

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of Study

The growth in municipal solid waste generation all over the world is due to urbanization, industrialization and population growth, together with improved living standards as it has been widely reported. The threat of environmental pollution stemming from indiscriminate solid waste disposal through open waste dumping has been haunting the human race since early times and is still growing due to poor waste disposal techniques prevalent in most developing countries. Karimi et al., (2018).

Solid Waste Management is one of the difficulties confronting most urban areas in the world today, especially in developing countries (Oyinloye, 2013). Waste reduction, recycling and waste transformation methods are normally used to reduce the quantity and toxicity of solid waste (Sener, 2004). Despite all the listed measures to consciously reduce the volume of waste from source, there will always be some quantity of waste that has no recycling value or by products of transformed wastes that still need a home for disposal. Hence, the need for a landfill site to safely, economically and hygienically dispose of these wastes. Landfills provide an efficient and environmentally sound disposal of waste that cannot be recycled, composted, combusted or processed in some manner (USEPA, 1995). Landfills can also serve as a backup waste management system in technologically advanced countries looking into total transformation of solid waste when recycling, composting or other facilities break down or are under routine maintenance. Over the years as technology evolved developed countries found out ways to reduce, reuse, recycle and properly dispose solid wastes through effective process management, however same cannot be said of developing and underdeveloped countries as solid waste management system is either nonexistent, not efficient or at the early stage and as

such waste generated has become a threat and menace to the environment. In the short term providing and siting waste disposal through landfill is an integral feature of all waste management plans due to the deteriorating effects it has on the environment and public health if neglected or relegated. The management of large volumes of solid wastes in terms of collection, sorting, storage, transportation and disposal with conventional methods has become really daunting. With incidences of indiscriminate dumping of all sorts of refuse and wastes by both residents and private waste contractors, management of solid has been made worse. Like expected, locations of landfill sites are prone to infections and sanitation related diseases like cholera, diarrhea, typhoid fever, malaria etc. Aside these listed ailments are a high amount of rodents that can lead to the deadly Lassa fever, unaesthetic view, and leachate from waste, stench all over the neighborhood with flies and scavenging birds that makes the environment unpleasant for the inhabitants there. Researchers have confirmed that residents living near waste treatment centers and landfills have unusual shortness of breath, eye irritation, hoarseness and/or dry throat, toothaches, tiredness, fairly frequent fever, joint and muscular pains among others. Hence, it's imperative to cite the best location for this necessary evil. Solid Waste management issues for local municipal authorities are a major environmental agenda at a growing frequency due to high population levels, rapid economic growth, unplanned development and rise in community living standards. Disease transmission, fire hazards, odor noise, air and water pollution, aesthetic view and economic losses are some of the problems connected with inappropriate management of domestic solid waste (Nwambuonwo and Mughele, 2012).

The increase in awareness of health and environmental issues in today's world, coupled with the passive competing demands on government for improvement on living standards and poverty alleviation, especially in Sub-Saharan Africa, has meant that in Nigeria, a lot more focus has had to be placed on appropriate and cost effective methods of dealing with waste

generated by a population that is growing by an average of 3% with Urban cities getting up to 5% increase per annum according to statista.com. Nigeria is currently facing considerable challenges in the area of solid waste management. These challenges could be due to high population growth, inadequate resource allocation and the shortage of skilled manpower, amongst other factors. This has led to rapidly filling up of the very few available dumping sites, thus increasing the risk of adverse environmental and public health impacts.

The recent outbreak of Cholera fever in Nigeria in 2010 which was described as the worst which was described as the worst in 30 years was attributed to the poor sanitary conditions in the cities resulting from improper waste management (www.myjoyonline.com, 2010). Many more epidemics have been suffered due to poor hygiene in the recent past with Lassa fever a notable mention. Previous experience has shown that problems, such as air pollution and groundwater contamination is associated with the siting and operation of Landfill sites. As a result of the impact of the problems arising from the siting and operation of landfills on nearby environments and communities where they are located, the public has become increasingly aware of their negative impacts (Erkut et al., 1991). As a result of the increasing awareness of the impacts of landfill sites, communities and individuals have developed a "Not in My Back Yard (NIMBY)" attitude towards siting of landfills. NIMBY is an important consideration in deciding on potential areas for a landfill. Associated problems with landfill sites could be reduced by implementing a proper and well-designed siting technique that involves parties such as planners, engineers, politicians, as well as representatives of the public (Wan et al., 2010). Therefore, in a landfill siting process, there are critical factors and constraints such as the allowable buffer distance of the site to access roads, residential or industrial areas, the topography of the area, etc. which are taken into account and carefully evaluated. The most suitable site that would be chosen after the evaluation process should not have any serious

adverse consequences on the environment, society and the economy, as well as conforming to existing land-use regulations and accepted by the public (Mohd-Din et al., 2008).

Just like almost every engineering project, many factors come into play when analyzing the most suited environment for siting dumps and solid wastes. Factors include but are not limited to: acquisition and legal factors, operation, development of the site and environmental factors more importantly.

1.2 Statement of Problem

The most used mode of solid waste disposal in most settlements in Benin City and Nigeria in general is uncontrolled dumping in places such as abandoned lands, valleys, beaches and drains which have serious adverse impacts on human life and the environment. The spike in urbanization and industrialization has however resulted in higher volume in waste generation, especially in the urban areas, which can no longer be adequately managed by dumping in open spaces which are now becoming less available (Godfrey, 1998).

Currently, solid waste management has become a major problem in Benin City, because only few legitimate open dumpsites exist to accommodate a large amount of waste generated daily. Unrecognized landfills are by every major marketplace due to little to no sensitization on the health hazard caused by improper waste management systems. This dump site is closer to residential areas and is not equipped with appropriate lining to prevent the contamination of underground water by leachate and spread of infections through run offs during rains.

Before decisions on where to situate a landfill is made, certain criteria need to be carefully studied and analyzed to select the most appropriate site that would have little or no environmental and economic impact and that would be accepted by the public and most importantly comply with regulations. Geographic Information System (GIS) and Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) has lessened the burden of the most vital and difficult part of waste management which is siting the landfill itself. Its ability to manage enormous amounts of

spatial data in different forms from various sources using GIS packages makes it an invaluable asset for site selection studies.

1.3 Aims and Objectives

1.3.1 Aims of Study

The main objective of the study was to identify and select suitable locations for a landfill site in the Benin-City using Geographic Information System (GIS) and a Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis based approach.

1.3.2 Objectives of Study

- i. To carry out a pairwise comparison of selection criteria;
- ii. To standardize the selection criteria to a common scale and perform weighted overlay Analysis in ArcGIS;
- iii. To produce a landfill site suitability index map;

1.4 Scope of Work

The area under study is the city of Benin. The research will combine Geographic Information System (GIS) and Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis using spatial data of important landfill suitability variables like geology, transportation networks, water bodies, and several other environmental factors in criticizing the suitability of the in situ landfills and checking if they meet already laid down regulations in siting landfills in Nigeria.

1.5 Justification of Study

According to WHO and NCDC (Nigeria Center for Disease Control), Edo state accounted for slightly over 35% of the Lassa fever endemic cases in Nigeria in 2020. 90-95% of human

infections are due to direct or indirect exposure to infected rats urine and faeces to household items and food. Inadequately sited and unmanaged landfills draw rodents to humans. Improperly siting of landfills is almost as dangerous as not siting landfills hence, the need proper study into the most appropriate site that would meet all the suitability analysis for landfills.

Aside proper siting, developing and maintaining an effective and efficient solid waste management system in the Benin-City requires the establishment and enforcement of legislation, by-laws and implementation of proper waste management practices that are unique enough to address the sanitation issues in the city and state in general. The availability of land and selecting the most environmentally and economically suitable site for the construction of a landfill site to receive the large amounts of waste generated is a major step towards solving the problem of solid waste management in the city.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter seeks to provide an evaluation of previous work done on suitability analysis of siting landfills and other related studies. The chapter also gives the definitions for key terms adopted in the study, relevant laws and regulation guiding the landfills in Nigeria and Edo state are also discussed and brief look into the relevant software and other related software and other related software are looked into.

2.1 GIS and REMOTE SENSING in Environmental Engineering

Geographic Information System has proven to be an efficient and effective tool when used in environmental management especially when it involves decision making and planning processes e.t.c. Its greatest strength lies in its ability to superimpose geo-data of varied types as well as manipulating it to come up with optimal results that aid decision. Hence, facilitating the best operations for environmental management and as a monitoring tool. As a management tool GIS is used in a wide spectrum of disciplines which include ecological management, fishery, water management, wildlife management, tourism, waste management, natural hazards prediction and management, agriculture, fire management, to mention but a few (Wang et al. 2009).

Applications of GIS are vast and cover almost every discipline that deals with decision making and space. As technology and science improves many other uses for GIS are being discovered hence incorporating more disciplines into its arrays of discipline. A few examples of it include: timely prediction of natural disasters and spotting the areas likely to be most affected, epidemic spread path, river navigation, management of complex wiring networks on power lines e.t.c. Technological improvement has given rise to the utilization of GIS that plays a major role for social development, environmental protection and management as well as economic boosting

purposes (Naire, 2010). GIS and Remote Sensing assist in environmental monitoring and this includes land-use cover changes, vegetation cover monitoring, forest protection as well as drought and fire and floods monitoring. Sener et al. (2006). GIS is also used for spatial analysis in environmental management, usually in site suitability analysis for various environmental projects that includes: municipal landfills, weather stations, mine dump sites, security, e.t.c.

While land suitability analysis is becoming a standard tool in environmental inventory and analysis, its application to sanitary landfill siting has been limited due to uncertainty about the factors which should be mapped, criteria for determining the relative degree of suitability for each factor, and limitations in an agency's file of available environmental data. This paper examines each of these aspects in comparing two case studies, Kenton and Campbell Counties, Kentucky, and Dane County, Wisconsin, which utilized area wide land suitability analysis as an element in sanitary landfill siting studies. Each of the approaches is briefly compared with techniques described in the literature, and the advantages and disadvantages of the techniques used are described.

Chang et al., (2008) in their study "GIS integrated approach for optimized landfill site selection" used the Fuzzy method to identify suitable sites for landfill in the lower RioGrande Valley region of Texas. Screening process for eliminating unsuitable land was done using ArcGIS software. Fuzzy multi criteria decision analysis was selected to be the most suitable landfill site. The operators used in actualizing this were 'Addition' and ' Multiplication' operations. The core of the study is fuzzy membership functions taking into account the uncertainties associated with some of the criteria which are sometimes unquantifiable such as impacts on historical sites in terms of odor, aesthetics etc. due to the landfill in the environs.

Karwan Alkaradaghi et al., (2021) studied the process suitability analysis of siting landfills using GIS and AHP in the governorate of Sulaymaniyah located in the north of Iraq with a population of 856,990. The GIS and AHP were used to carry out the procedure of siting landfill sites in the Sulaymaniyah governorate that didn't have a recognized landfill or waste management system in place prior. The following prerequisites necessary in siting landfills were considered: groundwater depth, urban area, rivers, villages, soil types, elevation, roads, slope, land use, archaeological sites, power lines, oil and gas fields, and geology. These criteria were used in the GIS, due to its high ability to manage and analyze various data. In addition, the AHP method was used to derive the weightings of criteria, through a matrix of pairwise comparison.

Delgado et al. (2010) compared three spatial decision support models which includes Binary Evidence, Boolean logic, and Overlapping index of multiple class maps. The constraints introduced in the study were selected as stipulated in the governmental regulations with respect to landfill site selection methods. The study shows that Boolean logic is easier and a more restrictive method than the other two methods. Binary evidence and overlapping index method requires assignment of weights to the factors considered in the study.

James LeBeau, (2007) describes the use of GIS and cartographic images for depicting the heat map for the distribution of various group crimes and calls for service helping the unit in analyzing and mapping areas of greater concern. GIS based crime mapping is a great way to visualize community problems and help channel appropriate attention to the areas it's mostly needed. The U.S. Department of Justice (2006) describes GIS as a tool that helps the department display geographic data using points or shapes corresponding to specific areas on a map to aid in crime mapping and strategic intelligence charting. Abbas et al, (2010) observes

that critical factors in the mapping process is its data acquisition methods, its accuracy and quality is vital to the essence of graphic representation as geographic data as a whole.

Ebrahim Esa and Mohamed Assen (2016) in their study "A GIS based land suitability analysis for sustainable agricultural planning in Gelda catchment, Northwest Highlands of Ethiopia" determined the suitable location to discern the spatial variation to suit the intended purpose. Low fertility areas due to irrigation activity, disadvantaged topography e.t.c. were identified to help farmers make more informed decisions for improved yield in a farming season. This makes suitability analysis in the evaluation of land a great tool in decision making in investment of lands to bring social and economic gains at minimum environmental costs. The methodology used for evaluation was Multi-Criteria Evaluation (MCE) and it's based on FAO (1976) guidelines that involves matching the diagnostic land quality against crop requirements and evaluating the suitability rates for each land quality factor.

Fidelis O. Ajibade et al (2019) has studied the combination of MCA and GIS in siting landfills in Ondo state, Nigeria for a design life of 30 years when he they highlighted Population explosion coupled with poor governance and land use planning is responsible for indiscriminate dumping of solid waste in unsuitable sites. Despite the availability of methods of siting landfills, many waste disposal methods in Akure are piled up in open sites making them unsafe. Due to the ineffective methods in Akure, they proffered and adopted the analysis of a number of required qualitative and quantitative issues for landfill site selection. The study was aimed at identifying suitable sites for solid waste disposal and management while considering all essential factors and rating criteria by integrating GIS with multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) in Akure, Ondo State while following standards for siting landfill formulated by the Environment Protection Agency (EPA) were employed in this study. The

criteria that are considered herein are: distance to drainage, land use, slope, distance to linear features, soil, geology, distance to the residence and road accessibility. These criteria were assigned fuzzy membership classes based on their importance in siting landfill. The fuzzy members of all criteria were overlaid to generate the final landfill site suitability map which were classified into five and they are as follows: not suitable (34.1%), less suitable (50.4%), moderately suitable (0.3%), suitable (0.02%) and highly suitable (15.5%). The Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) technique was employed in the selection of the landfill site with reverence to multiple criteria and the fuzzy membership classes in accordance with the standards of the EPA. The result of this study serves as a guide for further field survey.

Şener Başak (2004) in his research highlighted shortage of land for waste disposal to be a serious and growing potential problem in large urban areas. Although there are some efforts to reduce and recover the waste, disposal in landfills is still the most common method for waste destination. Inappropriate landfill sites always have negative impacts on the economic, ecological and environment. GIS and MDA were used to determine the most appropriate landfill area in the Ankara vicinity. For this purpose, sixteen input map layers including topography, settlements (urban centers and villages), roads (Highway E90 and village roads), railways, airport, wetlands, infrastructures (pipelines and power lines), slope, geology, land use, floodplains, aquifers and surface water are prepared and two different MCDA methods (Simple Additive Weighting and Analytic Hierarchy Process) are implemented in GIS environment. Comparison of the maps produced by these two different methods shows that both methods yield conformable results. Field checks also confirm that the candidate sites agree well with the selected criteria.

Stephen et al., (2008) in their research “A pairwise comparison of the effectiveness of selected active labor market programs in Germany” they studied the estimates of average effects of further vocational training, short training and job creation schemes on the employment prospects of participants. We compare participation in each program with non-participation as well as with participation in one of the other programs. Outcome variables are cumulated days spent in regular employment during the 3 and half years after program start as well as the share in regular employment at the end of the observation period.

Ebrahim Esa and Mohamed Assen (2016) in their study "A GIS based land suitability analysis for sustainable agricultural planning in Gelda catchment, Northwest Highlands of Ethiopia" determined the suitable location to discern the spatial variation to suit the intended purpose. Low fertility areas due to irrigation activity, disadvantaged topography e.t.c were identified to help farmers make more informed decisions for improved yield in a farming season. This makes suitability analysis in the evaluation of land a great tool in decision making in investment of lands to bring social and economic gains at minimum environmental costs. The methodology used for evaluation was Multi-Criteria Evaluation (MCE) and it's based on FAO (1976) guidelines that involves matching the diagnostic land quality against crop requirements and evaluating the suitability rates for each land quality factor.

Genemo Berisa and Yohanis Berhanu (2016) conducted research on the selection of suitable sites for the disposal of municipal solid waste generated from Jigjiga Municipality using GIS techniques. The existing open dumping systems in the town are not environmentally sound and socially acceptable as wastes have been dumped in inappropriate sites. The present study had integrated environmental and socio-economic criteria like proximity to road networks, distances from residences and important built up areas; surface water (river), boreholes and

reservoirs to select the most suitable landfill site in the study area. The result reveals that out of five candidate landfill sites, a site with reasonable size (24 ha), at optimum distance from residences (4.8 km) and accessible to the major roads (1 km) was nominated as the most suitable site.

Kamal_Jain and Y. Venkata Subbaiah (2007) thoroughly studied the importance of GIS in nation building. They discussed how the future success of economic growth policies depends a lot on infrastructure development. They reinforced how Remote sensing and GIS tools play a major role in various infrastructure development as several decisions taken by different planning agencies require spatial analysis of maps involving many parameters with the GIS based maps providing the most important sources for spatial analysis while remote sensing data provide latest and accurate maps when used in the GIS environment they become integrated. The main aim of the study was to study the growth and trend of urbanization around the city, as well as to locate the suitable sites for further urban development around the city. In this study, Roorkee town was considered and a site suitability map was prepared for 1967 and 1996 and the results are compared with land use maps of 1996 and 2003, respectively and found that urban development is following the methodology proposed. Eventually the site suitability map is prepared based on the 2003 land use map for further urban development.

2.2 GIS TECHNOLOGY

Hardware and Software are used collectively to complete this task. The hardware is the computer on which GIS operates. The software the functions and tools needed to capture the information, store, analyze, and display the geographic information in the form of maps or reports. All GIS software relies on an underlying database management system (DBMS) for storage and management of the geographic data. The GIS communicates with the DBMS to

perform queries and commands specified by the user. Their greatest strength lies in their ability to superimpose geo-data of varied types as well as manipulating it to come up with optimal results that aids decisions. As a management tool GIS is used in a wide spectrum of disciplines which includes ecological management, natural hazards prediction and management, agriculture, fire management, e.t.c (Wang et al 2009)

Applications of GIS are vast and cover almost every discipline that deals with decision making and space. As technology and science improves, many other uses for GIS unfold. Some uses of GIS include: timely prediction of natural disasters as well as spotting areas likely to be most affected, epidemic spread path, river navigation, management of complex wiring networks on power line e.t.c. GIS is also used for spatial analysis in environmental management usually in site suitability analysis for various environmental projects that includes: municipal landfills, weather stations, mine dump sites e.t.c. Solutions to various environmental problems with the application of GIS has been seen in diverse forms due to its proven know-how in environmental management, overtime it became almost every nation's ambition to key into this versatile technological entity so as to achieve their desired conducive environment for all as well as having long lasting data storage facility to attain sustainable development as it has come to be the major environmental global concern.

2.2.1 Requirements of GIS users

GIS technology would be of limited value if the interface is too cumbersome for people to navigate through. GIS users range from technical specialists who design and maintain the system to those who use it to help them do their everyday work. Usability is objective and subjective based on the required outcome. Objective measure is the user's interaction with the system to perform tasks while subjective measure means the attitude of users toward interaction or outcome of usability evaluation. A technically sound individual and one able to sort

geospatial data would be able to navigate their way around the GIS software at least for basic tasks.

2.2.2 Methods on operation

GIS operates according to a well-designed implementation plan and business rules, which are the models and operating practices unique to each organization. For many years, GIS has been considered to be too difficult, expensive and proprietary. The advent of graphical user interface (GUI), powerful and affordable hardware and software, and public digital data has broadened the range of GIS applications and brought GIS mainstream use.

2.2.3 ArcGIS

ArcGIS is a type of GIS used for mapping and obtaining geographic information maintained by the Environmental Systems Research_Institute (ESRI). Its use includes creating and using maps, compiling geographic data, analyzing mapped information, sharing and discovering geographic information, using maps and geographic information in a range of applications, and managing geographic information in a database.

In connection with modern information technology, GIS enables new forms of communication between people, not only in the fields of research but also in the entire communities (Nwankwoala et al., 2012). GIS has emerged as a powerful tool for saving, analyzing and displaying spatial data and using this data for decision making in several areas including engineering and environmental fields.

The use of ArcGIS technology has simplified the assessment of pollutant and environmental concerns, including landfills. Suitability analysis of landfills using remote sensing imagery is relatively inexpensive and can consistently offer spatial measurement of landfill siting criteria without much hassles. Remote sensing estimation of landfills is based on mapping the

relationship between remote sensing multi spectral signatures and measurements of ground truth data.

2.2.4 Benefits of GIS

Below are some of the numerous benefits highlighted by Farag (2010).

- I. Integrating Geographic Information for display and analysis within the framework of a single consistent system.
- II. Allowing manipulation and display of geographic knowledge in new and exciting ways.
- III. Automating Geographic Information and transferring them from paper to digital format.
- IV. Linking location and attributes of feature(s) within the framework of one system.
- V. Providing the ability to manipulate and analyze Geographic Information in ways that are not possible manually.
- VI. Automation of map making, production and updating.
- VII. Providing a unified database that can be accessed by more than one department or agency.
- VIII. Storing Geographic Information in coincident and continuous layers.

2.2.5 Data

This is the most important and expensive component of GIS. Collection and modelling of data are crucial elements of a successful system. There are two types of data in GIS: spatial data and attribute data. Spatial data describes the physical geography represented in a database, whereas attribute data is linked to the spatial data as they basically describe the spatial objects.

Geographic data, which can take a number of forms, is entered into a GIS using a technique called digitizing.

Generally, the source material and the standards of data development determine both the scale and precision of spatial datasets.

2.3 Google Earth

Google Earth is a computer program that renders a 3D representation of Earth based primarily on satellite imagery. The program maps the Earth by superimposing satellite images, aerial photography and GIS data onto a 3D globe, allowing users to see cities and landscapes from different angles. Users can explore the globe by entering addresses and coordinates, or by using a keyboard or mouse. The program can also be downloaded on a smartphone or tablet using a touch screen to navigate. Google earth is also able to show various kinds of images overlaid on the surface of the earth and is also a Web Map Service client (Bill Kilday et al 2018).

In addition to Earth navigation, Google Earth provides a series of other tools through the desktop application. Additional globes for the moon and mars are available, as well as a tool for viewing the night sky. The web based version of Google Earth also includes Voyager, a feature that periodically adds in program tours, often presented by scientists and documentarians (Kevin Manney, 2003).

2.3.1 Google Earth Images

Google Earth imagery is displayed in a digital globe, which displays the planet's surface using a single composited image from a far distance. When zoomed, the imagery evolves into different images of the same area with clearer detail, which varies in date and time from one area to the next. Before the launch of NASA and USGS's Landsat 8 satellite, Google relied partially from Landsat 7, which suffered from a hardware malfunction that left diagonal gaps

in images (USGS 2017). Google now uses Landsat 8 to provide imagery in a higher quality and with greater frequency. (Tech Crunch et al., 2016).

Imagery resolution ranges from 15 meters of resolution to 15 centimeters. For each of the earth, Google Earth uses digital elevation model data collected by NASA's shuttle Radar Topography Mission. (Farr et al., 2007) this creates the impression of 3D terrain, even where the imagery is only 2D.

Every image created from Google Earth using satellite data provided by Google Earth is a copyrighted map. Any derivative from Google Earth is made from copyrighted data which under US Copyright Law, may not be used except under the licenses Google provides.

2.3.2 Google Earth Features

Google Earth has numerous features which allow the user to learn about specific places. These are called "Layers", and include different forms of media, including photo and video. Some layers include tours, which guide the user between specific places orderly. Layers are created using the Keyhole Markup Language, or KML, which users can also use to create customized layers. (Keyhole Markup Language, 2012).

In December 2016, Google Earth added a new integration with Wikipedia and Panoramio. For the Wikipedia layer, entries are scrapped for coordinates via the Coordinate templates. There is also a community layer from the project Wikipedia World. The Panoramio layer features pictures uploaded by Panoramio users, placed in Google Earth and also includes a layer for user submitted panoramic photos, navigable in a similar way to Street view.

Google Earth includes multiple features that allow the user to monitor current events. In 2007, Google began offering users the ability to monitor traffic data provided by Google traffic in real time based on information crowdsourced from the GPS-identified locations of cell phone users. (Wang D, 2007).

2.4 CONCEPT OF SOLID WASTE

Solid waste is the general term used to describe non-liquid waste materials generated from domestic, agricultural, medical, commercial, industrial activities. Waste management is a global environmental issue which constitutes a very significant problem in today's world. (ESRI, 2001). Solid wastes are generally categorized into biodegradable and non-biodegradable. Biodegradable wastes are wastes capable of being decomposed and broken down into very small parts by biological processes especially by microorganisms while non-biodegradable wastes describe wastes that are barely impacted by biological processes thereby maintaining their components and structure for a long time.

2.5 WASTE MANAGEMENT

Waste management is now a mainstay challenge to the government and every other responsible authority associated with the management of waste in our present day society. With urbanization, industrialization, improved living standards, geometric rate of increase in population growth due to unprecedented rates of migration among others factors being some of the catalyst speeding up the cause for concern of waste in major cities; smaller and relaxed towns and villages aren't left out especially in a developing continent like Africa with irregular dumping of wastes and siting of landfills are the major cause for worries. However, while governments are stepping up efforts at protecting the environment and enacting laws geared towards public health through policy formulation, the citizenry and industrialists too must adopt ways of doing things to minimize the tons of waste generated. Solid waste management aims at reducing the amount of waste generated and improvement in the collection as well as the recovery of reusable materials and disposal of solid waste in a manner that is in accordance

with the best principles of public health, economics, and engineering, conservation of nature, aesthetics and environmental considerations in general. (Tchobanoglous et al., 1993).

Indiscriminate dumping of wastes and the inability of responsible agencies to collect them promptly for final disposal at designated landfills results in generation of odors in habited areas, breeding rodents and flies that can lead to epidemics like Lassa fever and even unprecedented fire outbreaks in dry seasons.

Integrated solid waste management (ISWM) is the standard for the implementation and design of new solid waste management methods and for the analysis of operational systems. ISWM evaluates the peculiarities associated with a region and develops the most appropriate and effective waste management system to meet the local needs and existing conditions. It seeks the best options for waste management, with emphasis on evaluating all available strategies to deliver more sustainable systems. (Fei-Baffoe, 2010). Solid waste management considered under ISWM systems are:

- I. Source Reduction
- II. Waste Recycling
- III. Waste Transformation
- IV. Landfilling

These four systems are to be interactive and hierarchical as the next should only be considered after the previous has been fulfilled or doesn't fit.

2.5.1 Source Reduction

Source reduction or waste prevention involves reduction in the volume and toxicity of waste generated. This stage should be practiced by all parties which includes the consumer, manufacturers and government. Manufacturer should research effective ways to minimize the volume of raw materials used and also the toxicity of the materials, consumers can play their

role in source reduction by patronizing only manufacturers whose by-products are environmentally safe and renewable compared to similar products while the government can provide tax abatement and financial subsidies to companies whose by-products are biodegradable and environmental friendly. This is the most effective way to minimize the costs of disposal of waste as the problem of the volume and toxicity is managed by the prevention of its generation.

However, a drawback to this is it's difficult to implement without distorting trade and commerce.

2.5.2 Recycling of Waste

Recycling is presumably the most accepted and easy to carry out among all the waste management practices (Tchobanoglous, 2003). Recycling reduces the usage of finite resources, raw materials and energy used in the manufacture of products, conserves landfill space and the creation of jobs and revenue generation (USEPA, 2005). The success of recycling rests greatly on the consumers as they start the recycling cycle by segregating useful by-products at source and then end the cycle by purchasing products from recycled contents. Public sensitization and general involvement is critical to the implementation of recycling as it will only yield good results where economic conditions support it and not when it's mandated. Recycling can however have adverse impacts when it is not practiced in a regulated and environmentally responsible manner (Tchobanoglous, 2003).

2.5.3 Waste Transformation

This is the process of reducing the volume of waste for efficient management. It involves the recovery of reusable materials and recycling them into new ones and generation of energy. Depending on the energy requirements for the host community, waste transformation can be

either profitable or unwarranted because of the associated running costs. A major drawback on waste transformation aside the cost is the relatively high degree of sophistication that is required to operate safely and economically.

2.5.4 Landfilling of Waste

Of the four management options, landfilling is perhaps the most necessary and independent as the others produce residuals that have no reuse value and need a home for disposal. A landfill is a large area of excavated land that is specifically designed and built to receive wastes (USEPA 2005). Siting of landfills needs to fulfill many buffer distances to roads, living areas, and rivers e.t.c. due to the unpleasant stench the compiled waste brings which makes nobody want it around them even when everyone needs it. The landfills are constructed with liners that consists of successive layers of compacted clay and/or geosynthetic material to prevent the migration of landfill leachate and gas so as to prevent pollution of groundwater as this leachate contains heavy metals like mercury and lead that are detrimental to human lives. Improper siting construction of landfills have the potential to cause great damage to the environs and people around it. Landfilling of waste is being opposed severally especially due to the reduction in economic value it brings to its environment and numerous hazards, but it would always remain a very vital part of the waste management cycle as every waste management technique requires landfills at the very end of their operations.

The American Society of Civil Engineers (ASCE) has defined a sanitary landfill as a method of disposing of refuse on land without creating nuisances or hazards to public health or safety by utilizing the principles of engineering to confine the refuse to the smallest practical area, to reduce it to the smallest practical volume, and to cover it with a layer of earth at the conclusion of each operation, or as such more frequent intervals as may be necessary. A true sanitary landfill is not an open dump.

2.6 LANDFILL SITE SELECTION

Identification of suitable locations is perhaps the most difficult and contentious stage of every waste management process as it involves the evaluation of all available land for landfills and selecting the most suited after various suitability analysis. A survey on the community is done and sites are identified that would meet all the economic, technical and environmental requirements as well as one that is accepted by the host community. The design, siting and construction determine the extent of the impact of the landfill on public health and the immediate environment. A poorly sited facility will have an immense adverse impact on the public and the environment as well as increased cost of operation (Redford, 2016).

2.6.1 Siting Criteria

The first most important stage in landfilling is the selection of a suitable site. The site selection of solid waste landfills requires a careful examination and evaluation of all of the components of landfill construction and operation that could potentially result in adverse effects on the environment (NTEPA, 2013). The selected site must meet the laid down minimum requirements of local and national regulations and have minimum impact in the social, economic and environmental well-being. Some areas are off limits due to the high level of risk a potential landfill poses to their economy and environment, these areas are referred to as exclusive zones.

2.6.1.1 Environment

The presence of landfill would always have a negative impact on the environment either directly or indirectly. Exclusive zones like schools, tourist attractions, and recreational centers e.t.c should be stayed far away from as landfills gradually deteriorate the living standards of

flora and fauna around it. Hence, when decisions are to be made the impact on the immediate environment should be evaluated carefully for each of the potential sites.

2.6.1.2 Land Area and Availability of Suitable Material

The design life of the project should be considered due to the technicalities involved in siting landfills. Only sites with adequate land area able to accommodate the forecasted volume of waste for the next 20-30 years are to be considered. The material at the site should be easy to spread, compact and impermeable. The soil will be used as a cover material at the close of each day to prevent the migration of leachate and landfill into the environment.

2.6.1.3 Economic Factors

Although distance from habited areas is encouraged, however, if the facility is too far from the generation centers, the cost of hauling and constructing access roads to the site may become high. Siting landfills not too far from already existing roads should be adopted to minimize the cost of its construction and operation.

The land value for potential sites must be taken into consideration since it has an economic bearing on the project cost, as lands with higher use values will attract higher compensation when compared to lesser valued lands with lower cost of acquisition.

2.6.1.4 Topography

Finding the balance between flat surfaces that would be subjected to flooding in the rainy season and steep surfaces that would be eroded by erosion and other operational difficulty makes the topographic profile of a potential site vital for consideration. Lin Kao(2005) suggested that the appropriate slope of potential landfill sites should be about 8%-12%.

2.6.1.5 Geology

Areas with low permeability in situ geological formulation are always preferred for Landfilling. Hence, suitable geology is an important criterion for landfilling suitability analysis to ensure the contaminants of leachate in unlined dumps doesn't permeate the soil. Fractured crystalline rock has low permeability rate and will allow less fluid when compared to poorly cemented sandstones with a high porosity which easily allows fluid to pass through. A site with predominantly sandstone bedrock is less preferred for landfill construction as compared to sedimentary bedrocks such as shale and limestone.

2.7 Importance of Landfill siting

In developing countries where laws enacted to clamp down on improper waste offenders are taken with a sizable amount of laxity, final disposal is usually a matter of transporting the collected waste to the nearest available open source and discharging them. According to AIT, (2005) most solid waste is disposed of indiscriminately and in an environmentally unacceptable manner through open or controlled dumping in Africa. Jung et al, (2005) establishes that open dumping has potential to reduce environmental quality in neighborhoods and can also pose a threat to public health and the environment.

Thus siting a landfill should be considered more than simply deciding the location of waste facilities as it's a process that occurs amid a complexities of geographic, cognitive, affective and political responses (Kraft & Clary, 1991).

2.8 RELEVANT REQUIREMENTS AND REGULATIONS IN EDO STATE

In Nigeria, landfill siting guidelines are developed by each state, but they are oriented based on the NESREA (National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency)

which is the Nigeria equivalent of EPA in America. The NESREA has their guidelines and requirements regarding landfill locationing, designs and operational criteria. According to the Edo state ministry of environment set up by the Edo State Environmental Edict of 1994 - The State would protect and develop general environmental laws as well as monitor and regulate disposal of solid, gaseous and liquid wastes from facilities, it would monitor air, water, land and soil in the state to determine pollution levels. It further defines a solid waste disposal area should not be sited in an area where the Edo state ministry of environmental Quality finds the solid waste activities will have a detrimental effect on the waters of the state. General standard practice forbids landfills to be sited with areas of floodplains, unstable areas and seismic impact zones. Patrick and Philip (2002) emphasized that areas with poor foundation conditions are not appropriate to construct a landfill because siting a landfill over a permeable formation such as gravel, sand or fractured bedrock can pose a significant threat to groundwater quality and damage to surrounding circumstances.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Description of the study area

3.1.1 Location

Benin City is the administrative capital of Edo state, of the Southern region of Nigeria. It lies between Longitudes $5^{\circ}30'$ and $5^{\circ}45'E$ and Latitude $6^{\circ}30'N$. It is situated approximately 40 kilometers north of the Benin River and 320 kilometers by road east of Lagos. The city has a land area of about 1,204 Km². Edo South senatorial District consists of seven local government areas (LGAs) namely: Egor, Oredo, Orhionmwon, Ikpoka-Okha, Ovia North East, Ovia South West, Uhunmwonde.

Figure 3.1: Map showing the study area

3.1.2 Climate

The city is typically tropical with two recognizable annual seasons, the dry and wet seasons. The first and most pronounced rainy season extends from late April to the end of July and the second season is from August to October. Annual mean rainfall is 1339mm with a fairly uniform temperature ranging between 28⁰C and 35⁰C all year round. Torrential rains are the norm with bright sunshine and a high humidity throughout the year. Sunshine duration for most of the year averages 7 hours per day. Relative humidity is usually high throughout the year between 70%-80% in the dry season and 75%-80% in the wet season.

3.1.3 Geology and Soil

The municipality is underlain by sedimentary formation of the South Sedimentary Basin. Most of its geology is marked by top reddish earth, composed of ferruginised or literalized clay sand. These sediments spread across the southern fringes of the Anambra Basin and mark the upper facies off flaps of the Niger Delta.

Catherine Imhangulaya (2012) describes the formation to be about 1830m thick at the seashore but thins landwards and the sedimentary suits of the Benin Formation dip 2° - 8° south. Geologically, the Benin Region comprises 1) the Benin formation; 2) alluvium; 3) drift/topsoil and 4) Azagba-Ogwashi formation.

3.1.4 Population

Benin-City is estimated to be around 1,727,000 in 2020, with an average yearly growth rate of about 3.2% and a socio demographic showing males to be about 52% and females to take the remaining 48% of the total population. Using the average annual growth rate of 3.2%, the projected population of the city is expected to be around 2,366,400 in 2030, 3,242,500 in 2040 and 4,443,000 in 2050.

The 2020 gubernatorial election statistics presents a fairly the number of registered voters to be estimated to be around 1,281,414 according to INEC which covers residents 18 years and above as at 2020. These statistics project figures of the population of the city since the volume of waste is directly proportional to population.

3.1.5 Topography and Drainage

Topography refers to how high or low the land surface is. The area is commonly undulating with few scraps ranging between 150 meters and 180 meters above the sea level and the land rises from about 250 meters above sea level. This has an important effect on the environment in creating watersheds, large expanses of stagnant water bodies, deep trenches and gullies as well as leaching of soil nutrients.

The municipality is drained by the Ikpoba River. There is enough groundwater potential for borehole construction for domestic and other uses within the municipality. The high precipitation experienced in the municipality supports farming activities without irrigation. Rainfall is the main water source for agricultural activities which continues all throughout the year.

3.2 PAIRWISE COMPARISON CHART (PCC)

Of the many important steps in a decision making methods, getting accurate estimate of the vital data is most important. Pairwise comparisons charts are used to determine the relative importance of each alternative in terms of each criterion and/or and prioritization of several criteria for the completion of a project. In this Analytical Hierarchy Process, a decision maker has to express his opinion about the value of a unit pairwise comparison at a time. Each decision has a linguistic phrase like “A is more important than B”, or “A is of equal importance as B”,

or “A is less important than B” and so on. However, the concern of this research is not the linguistic phrase but instead in the numerical values which should be associated with this statement.

For this research, a pairwise comparison chart of different suitability criteria for siting a landfill in Benin-City. The listed suitability criteria that would be used are as follows:

- i. Settlement
- ii. Rivers and Streams
- iii. Rail track
- iv. Slope
- v. Road network
- vi. Power lines
- vii. Geology

3.2.1 Pairwise Comparison of Landfill Suitability Criteria

3.2.1.1 Settlement: The comparison of the criteria is a subjectivity of the user. Settlement was prioritised due to the effect improper siting of landfills would have to the homes of the major players. Too close landfills to the homes of people would bring a lot of discomfort from rodents, scavengers, foul smell which would cause ill health to people around the landfill. Hence it got the nod over every other criterion.

3.2.1.2 Rivers and Streams: This criterion was picked as the fourth most important criteria for siting landfill behind Settlement, slope and geology. This is because the slope and geology of an area determines the amount of leachate that can seep into groundwater and surface water.

3.2.1.3 Rail Track: Rail line was assigned the least in the prioritise index not because it is not an important factor but because it would cause the least amount of constraint and health hazard when sited in an isolated rail line and not one close to train station and settlements.

3.2.1.4 Slope: This criterion was ranked second most important in the pairwise comparison chart. This is because the steepness of a slope poses increased hazards for maintenance and monitoring as well as allows for increase flowrate in the velocity of toxins into groundwater which is harmful to both flora and fauna.

3.2.1.5 Road Network: Roads in the PCC was divided into two namely Major roads and Minor roads. Both criteria were fourth and fifth least important respectively. They were ranked only above Power lines and Railways because they are they are also needed for accessibility to the landfills.

3.2.1.6 Power Lines: This criterion is ranked only second to the least on PCC. This is because with proper management causalities and environmental hazards can be minimised to the barest minimum as power lines are sited away from settlement.

3.2.1.7 Geology: the geological formation of an area was ranked third on the prioritise list behind settlement and slope because the geological formation determines if toxins would find their way into ground water.

3.3 DATA AND MATERIALS

3.3.1 Data collection

Data were obtained from literature reviews, internet sources, Field data obtained from Global Positioning System (GPS) coordinates of some selected areas within the study area.

3.3.2 Software Used

Data extraction, editing, management and analysis was completed using ArcGIS 10.0 by ERSI. All vector and raster data types were converted into a common coordinate system and a vector format acceptable by the software. The Pairwise comparison for prioritizing the various selection criteria was done in an Excel spreadsheet.

3.3.3 Pairwise Comparison Chart of Selection Criteria

According to Malczewski (2006), a study on GIS-based multi-criteria decision analysis showed that the pairwise comparison method was the most widely used procedure for estimating criterion weights when dealing with GIS-MCDA applications. This method can be applied in many decision making situations including study of preferences, voting systems, land suitability analysis and environmental impact assessment, site selection problems e.t.c.

In this approach, a matrix is generated from a list of factors that affects our siting criteria. These factors are pitched against each other and two objectives are compared at a time. The more important criterion is given a 1 on its row and the less favored a 0 in its own row. The result is collated at the end and the various suitability criteria are ranked. In this research, pairwise comparison was completed from comparison of various researches.

3.4 METHODS

Spatial analysis tools provided by the ArcGIS software have been integrated with the multi-criteria decision making procedure to facilitate the selection of a suitable landfill site for the Benin-City. Evaluation of criteria needed for landfill site selection in Benin-City was identified. National guidelines such as the Federal Environmental Protection Agency (FEMA) of Nigeria landfill siting guidelines, National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA), Edo State Waste Management Board (ESWMB) development guidelines and other international sources like the USEPA and relevant literature were used and in all seven important criteria were identified namely; Surface water, Slope, Geology, Settlement, Rail lines, Power lines and Roads network. ArcGIS 10.0 was used in creating landfill siting criteria layers as shown in the methodological flow chart below.

Figure 3.2: Research Methodological flow

3.4.1 Classify Parameters into Constraints and Factors

The relevant siting criteria were classified into constraints and factors, and these constraints and factors were identified by making reference to the Nigerian regulations, international best practices, as well as from relevant literature related to the study area.

Constraints criteria helps to render some areas unsuitable according to the regulation thereby making it impossible for landfill sites to be sited in these areas due to a possible threat to the general public health or conflict with the regulation. The areas that didn't meet the criteria were termed unsuitable and were screened out by using the overlay function in GIS.

3.4.2 Standardization of Criterion Scores

The GIS database is developed during this process. The various criteria are standardized to a common scale before they are combined in the GIS environment. This is done using a Spatial Analyst tool in ArcGIS 10.0 software. According to Drobne et al (2009), the standardization of evaluation criteria is sometimes referred to as a process of reclassifying values into a statement of set membership. The higher value of the standardization scale represents the case of being more likely to belong to the decision set and vice versa. To reduce grading complexities, a grading value of 1 to 3 was used for all standardization criterion map layers to a common unit. Each criterion was reclassified into three main categories: (1) Unsuitable, (2) Suitable, and (3) Most Suitable.

3.4.2.1 Rivers and Streams

Contamination of water bodies due to uncontrolled disposal of waste is one of the major issues in today's world. Any water body be it streams, lakes, rivers or impoundments should be taken into account in the selection process of landfill sites. Landfill is home to all sorts of harmful toxins that can leach into water bodies and can very easily contaminate nearby surface water and even groundwater when not properly constructed. This poses danger to the aquatic ecosystem, human and environment in general. It is therefore recommended that these facilities are sited far away from water bodies. According to the National Environmental Standards Regulations and Enforcement Agency Act (NESREA) of 2007, a buffer of at least 300meters should be observed around ponds, dams and lakes with a smaller buffer of 100meters for rivers. No drinking water should be sited within 500meters down the slope of the proposed landfill, except adequate measures are placed to protect such water bodies from any potential contamination. (WHO, 2004).

For this research work, distances less than 300 meters from water bodies are considered unsuitable for landfill siting and given the rank 1, while distances between 300 meters and 500 meters are considered suitable and given the rank 2, while for distances that are greater than 500 meters are considered most suitable and ranked 3.

3.4.2.2 Roads Network

Road criterion is divided into two layers. This is because the buffer distance a major road network needs is different from the distance required for feeder or minor roads. This subdivision is due to the difference in the appropriate buffer zone with respect to the importance of the road network. However, Lin & Kao, (1999) in their study stated that; to minimize the cost of constructing access roads to the landfill site, potential sites should be as close as possible to an existing road network. According to a report by the World Bank (2004), big landfills serving municipal and metropolitan areas should be sited in areas that require less than 10 Km of new access roads to be constructed and less than 3 Km of new access roads for those meant for smaller cities. According to the research done by Allen (2001), he suggested landfills sited less than 1 km away from roads and highways are not suitable.

Upon the consideration of all the above suggestions, the following classification was done for the two layers. For major roads, areas between 0 to 500 meters and above 10 Km were considered as unsuitable and scored 1, those within 500m to 2000m were considered most suitable and given the maximum score of 3, while areas beyond 2000 m were considered suitable and given the score 2. For minor roads, areas within 100m are termed unsuitable and scored the least score of 1, those within 100 m and 1000 m are considered most suitable and given the maximum score of 3, while those beyond 1000 m are considered as suitable and given a score of 2. Only sites that balance and meet the two criteria are considered for landfills.

3.4.2.3 Settlement

In this research, just like done in the roads, settlement areas were subdivided into two layers. These are urban and industrial areas, and the villages and hamlets. This is to help us to apply unique and appropriate buffer zone distances to the two layers. According to the NESREA (2007), there should be a buffer zone of 5000 m between residential areas and a landfill site. In a research done by Allen (2001), he stated that proximity to urban centers should be at least 5000 m and 500 m from isolated settlements Cantwell (1999), also suggested a 1000 m buffer for settlements with a human population of more than 500 and for all other settlements having a population less than 500, a 500 m buffer distance should be provided. However, Sener (2004), argued that due to economic considerations like cost of transportation and turnover costs, a landfill ought to be situated no more than 10 km from the urban area or waste generation centers.

Upon careful consideration of existing national regulation and relevant literature, the following buffer zones were adopted for Industrial and Urban areas and Villages and Hamlets. For industrial and urban areas; distances less than 5 km and greater than 30 km are unsuitable and given a ranking of 1, sites at distances between 5000 m to 10 km were considered most suitable and given a maximum score of 3 and that of those between 10 km and 30 km were considered suitable and given a score of 2. For villages and hamlets, areas less than 1000 m were considered unsuitable and given a score of 1, between 1000 m and 2000 m were considered suitable and scored 2, while areas beyond 2000 m were considered most suitable and given a score of 3.

3.4.2.4 Rail Lines

For rail lines, buffer distance for rail lines isn't explicitly stated in the NESREA (2007) code, this criterion however has been included in this research since there is a designated rail line

rack that runs through the city. According to Sener et al. (2006), a landfill site should not be located within 500 m from an existing rail line. This is to give room for future rail line expansion and to avoid nuisance. Areas within 500 m from an existing rail line were given a score of 1 and those between 500 m to 1000 m were given a score of 2, while areas beyond 1000 m were considered most suitable with a score of 3.

3.4.2.5 Power Lines

According to the Town and Regional Planning Law, which stipulates a mandatory distance of 5.5m, 15.5m and 25m setback on either side of the transmission lines for low tension, 11KV and 33KV lines. Areas that were within 30 m from the center of a high tension voltage line were considered unsuitable and given a score of 1 and areas between 30 m to 100 m were considered as suitable and scored 2, while areas beyond 30 m were considered most suitable and given a score of 3.

3.4.2.6 Slope

A Digital Elevation Model (DEM) of the study area was used to generate a slope map. Areas characterized by flat gradients less than 2% or by steep gradients greater than 10% where stability of slopes could be problematic are not suitable for siting a landfill. Therefore, areas with gradients less than 2% and greater than 15% will be unsuitable for landfill, areas with a slope between 10% and 15% are suitable, but areas with a slope between 2% and 10% will be most suitable for a landfill.

3.4.2.7 Geology

The formation is characterized by top reddish to reddish brown lateritic massive fairly indurated clay and sand. This is often marked with reticulate mudcracks.

The Benin formation which makes up about 95% of the region is considered most suitable hence, it's given the highest score of 3 while the remaining geological formations are considered unsuitable and given 1.

3.4.3 Weighted Overlay Analysis

The resultant datasets were reclassified into a common measurement scale of 1 to 3 so as to make it possible for combining the various criteria. This scale determines the suitability level of a particular location. Possible landfill locations were determined by a measurement scale value that indicates high suitability and vice versa.

In this study, areas with a scale value of 3 were most suitable, that of 2 were suitable and 1 were unsuitable for locating a landfill. This was done in ArcGIS, the reclassify tool in the Spatial Analyst tool box. With all the nine datasets set to a common scale, the next step was to combine them using the weights generated from the pairwise comparison matrix to obtain the suitability index map.

Table 3.1: Pairwise Comparison Matrix

CRITERIA	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	Total
1. Settlements	-	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	7
2. Rivers and Streams	0	-	0	0	1	1	1	1	4
3. Geology	0	1	-	0	1	1	1	1	5
4. Slope	0	1	1	-	1	1	1	1	6
5. Major Roads	0	0	0	0	-	1	1	1	3
6. Minor Roads	0	0	0	0	0	-	1	1	2
7. Railway	0	0	0	0	0	0	-	0	0
8. Power Lines	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	-	1

Table 3.2: Datasets Standardization

Criteria	Unsuitable (1)	Suitable (2)	Most Suitable (3)
Distance to Streams and Rivers	<300m	300m – 500m	>500m
Distance to Roads (Major Roads)	<500m / >10km	2000m – 10km	500m – 2000m
Distance to Roads (Minor Roads)	<100m / >5000m	1000m – 5000m	100m – 1000m
Distance to Settlement	<5km / >30km	10km – 30km	5km – 10km
Slope	<2% / 15%	10% - 15%	2% - 10%
Rail Line	<500m	500m – 1000m	>1000m

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 SUITABILITY EVALUATION CRITERIA

GIS analysis and Multi-criteria evaluation coupled with overlay operation were carried out for all constraints and criteria. The above operations were used to create suitability maps showing unsuitable, suitable and most suitable land areas for siting landfills in Benin City. The classified layers were overlaid on one another using their relative weights of importance from the pairwise matrix and the final suitability map was obtained.

4.1.1 Suitability Results and Discussion of Rail Line

Figure 4.1 shows the rail line passed through the study area and was considered as one of the constraints in siting a landfill. According to Sener et al., (2006) Landfills should not be situated within 500m radius of a rail line. In this study, areas within 500m from the rail line were considered unsuitable and restricted for the use of a landfill. Distances between 500m to 1000m were classified as suitable and beyond 1000 m from the rail line were considered most suitable and ranked 3. Table 4.1 below shows the ranking for the various buffer distances.

Figure 4.1 explains the areas as they were classified into three categories according to how suitable they are for the purpose of landfill based on the distance from the existing rail line in the study area.

From the table, 31.43 km², representing a mere 0.29% of the total land area of the study area is classified as unsuitable for siting a landfill while 226.83% representing 2.11 km² is classified as suitable for siting a landfill. The most suitable areas for siting a landfill based on the rail line criteria was 10503.93 km² representing 97.6% of the total study area.

Table 4.1: Classification of Rail line suitability analysis

Distance from Rail Line (m)	Ranking	Land Area (Km ²)	Land Area (%)
0 – 500	1	31.43	0.29
500 – 1000	2	226.83	2.11
> 1000	3	10503.93	97.6

Figure 4.1: Buffer Zones determined for Rail Line in Benin-City

4.1.2 Suitability Result and Discussion for Road Network

Like earlier stated in the methodology, the road criterion was divided into two layers; the major roads and minor roads. This is so because different buffer distances are required for mapping out restrictions zones for highways and feeder roads when it comes to siting a landfill.

For Road Network as illustrated in figure 4.2a and 4.2b, a buffer of 500m for Highways and 200m for feeder roads were mapped out as restricted areas so as to avoid the odor noise and nuisance caused by rodents and other scavenging animals crossing the roads. However, a good landfill ought not to be too far away from existing roads, so that the construction of new access roads is avoided and travel time is reduced for landfill transport vehicles. Hence, areas between 500m and 2000m for Highways and between 100m and 1000m for feeder roads are considered most suitable and distances above 2000m for highways and above 1000m for feeder roads are considered moderately suitable.

Figures 4.2a and 4.2b also show buffer zones determined for Major Roads and Minor roads respectively. For Major Roads, a land area of 227.08 km² representing 2.12% is considered unsuitable for the siting of a landfill according to the highway criterion. A land area of 9776.66 km² and 727.02 km² representing 91.11% and 6.78% of land area are classified as most suitable and suitable respectively according to the highway criterion. That of minor roads is shown in Table 4.2b, a land area of 1246.8 km² representing 13.15% is considered unsuitable for the siting of a landfill according to the highway criterion. A land area of 4070.82 km² and 4166.35 km² representing 42.92% and 43.93% of land area are classified as most suitable and suitable respectively according to the highway criterion.

Table 4.2a: Classification of Major Roads suitability analysis

Distance from Major Roads (m)	Ranking	Land Area (km²)	Land Area (%)
0 – 500	1	227.08	2.12
500 – 2000	2	9776.66	91.11
>2000	3	727.02	6.78

Table 4.2b: Classification of Minor Roads suitability analysis

Distance from Minor Roads (m)	Ranking	Land Area (km ²)	Land Area (%)
0 – 100	1	1246.8	13.15
100 – 1000	2	4070.82	42.92
>1000	3	4166.35	43.93

Figure 4.2a: Buffer Zone determined for Highway in Benin-City

Figure 4.2b: Buffer Zone for feeder roads in Benin-City

4.1.3 Suitability Results and Discussion of Settlement

Figure 4.3 below describes the settlement map of Benin-City with suitable areas a landfill can be sited. From the figure it can be inferred that the Central Business District of the city is at the center as majority of the activities are carried on there which also means majority of the waste would be generated in that region. Hence, every perimeter below 500m are restricted areas due to possible environmental and health hazards that landfills comes with. Distances just above the restricted areas up to 2000m i.e. distances between 500m to 2000m are however considered most suitable as landfills should be sited not too far from where it is generated. Distances above 2000m are considered moderately suitable.

From Table 4.4a which contains classes determined for the urban centers criteria, 13.15% of the study area is classified as unsuitable for landfills, 42.92% classified as most suitable and 43.93% classified as suitable for landfills.

Table 4.3: Classification of Settlement suitability analysis

Distance from Settlement (m)	Ranking	Land Area (km ²)	Land Area (%)
0 – 100	1	4268.63	41.61
100 – 1000	2	1920.23	18.72
>1000	3	4068.78	39.67

Figure 4.3: Buffer Zone for settlement in Benin-City

4.1.4 Suitability Results and Discussion for Streams and Rivers

The suitability results of rivers and streams are shown in Figure 4.1. The level of purity of streams and rivers is a factor that influences the buffer distance for water bodies. The purer the water the farther a landfill is expected to be sited so that toxins and leachate do not leach into the water body.

In the study, a buffer zone of 300 m as suggested by the USEPA was created around rivers, streams and lakes in the study area. Areas within 300m perimeter is restricted and unsuitable, between 300 m and 500 m is suitable and beyond 500 m is most suitable for siting a landfill as shown.

Table 4.1 shows the various classes obtained for this criterion according to their suitability for siting a landfill. From the suitability results, 3.09% of the total land area in the Benin City representing 321.23km² fall within areas classified as unsuitable and ranked 1. The class representing suitable sites covers 1.93% of the study area representing 201.32km² and ranked 2. A land area of 9886.98km² representing 94.98% of the study area and considered most suitable according to the rivers and streams criteria and is ranked 3.

Table 4.4: Classification of Streams and Rivers suitability analysis

Distance from Strems and Rivers (m)	Ranking	Land Area (km ²)	Land Area (%)
0 – 100	1	321.23	3.09
100 – 1000	2	201.32	1.93
>1000	3	9886.98	94.98

Figure 4.4: Buffer Zone for Streams and Rivers in Benin-City

4.1.6 Compatibility Results and Discussion for slopes

According to the Ghana Landfill Guidelines (2002) the slope of an area is one of the basic parameters considered when deciding on potential landfill sites. The guideline suggested areas with gradient less than 2%, groundwater i.e. springs and seepages where a sufficient unsaturated zone separates the groundwater and the waste body are not suitable for landfills. Areas with gradients greater than 10%, are also considered not suitable as the runoff rates will be too high when it rains. High runoffs rate leads to a decrease in infiltration that carries contaminants through the entire length the runoff water can travel. The vicinity is liable to contamination from the leachate that has been carried away from the containment area by the runoff from the landfill, especially surface waters.

In this study, areas with slopes between 2% and 10% were considered most suitable for the construction of a landfill and ranked 3, slopes between 10% and 15% were considered suitable and ranked 2 and areas with a slope less than 2% and greater than 15% were considered unsuitable and ranked 1. Figure 4.5 shows areas determined for slope according to suitability. Figure 4.7 and Table 4.7 show the suitability results for slope. A land area of 2009.11km² representing 18.69% of the study area has a slope gradient less than 2% and greater than 15% was classified as unsuitable for landfill. Areas with a slope gradient between 10% and 15% had a land area of 704.57km² representing 6.55% of the study area were classified as suitable, while areas with a slope gradient between 2% and 10% were classified as most suitable and had a total land area of 8048.51km representing 74.8% of the study area.

Table 4.5: Classification of Slopes suitability analysis

Slope value (%)	Ranking	Land Area (km²)	Land Area (%)
0 – 2, >15	1	2009.11	18.69
10 – 15	2	704.57	6.55
2 – 10	3	8048.51	74.8

Figure 4.5: Buffer Zone for Slopes of Benin-City

4.1.9 Results of Suitability Index

Figure 4.6: Suitability Index Map

4.2 SELECTION OF MOST SUITABLE SITES

Figure 4.6 shows the weighted overlay results of the various suitability criteria for siting Landfills. The majority filter tool in ArcGIS was used to filter out those small areas to get a more presentable results and also get a site with good enough design life. Some parts of Ovia North and Uhumwonde were discovered to be the most suitable areas for siting of landfill.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 CONCLUSION

The selection of a site for landfill for the use of solid waste disposal with all the necessary suitability analysis is a complex process which requires intentionally evaluating various factors like economic factors, environmental constraints, existing regulation and social cultural factors. This research used GIS combined with MCDA in the selection of a suitable site for a landfill for managing solid waste in Benin-City.

The various criteria used in determining suitable landfill were obtained mainly from literature reviews and relevant organizations. The pairwise comparison used in comparing and assigning weights based on importance to the selection criteria. From this study, it can be inferred that pairwise comparison enables decision makers by helping to analyse multiple criteria within a short time frame and it also enables quick readjustment of the criteria weights.

The selection criteria were made ready as input map layers and standardized to a common scale with the reclassifying tool in ArcGIS 10.0. Combination of all the selection criteria was done using a weighted overlay tool which helped to minimize the complexities that would have arisen from combining the various landfill site selection data from various sources.

A landfill site for solid waste disposal suitability index map was produced after performing overlay analyses using the weights of importance of the selection criteria. The landfill site for solid waste the suitability index map showed areas that were Most Suitable, Suitable and Unsuitable for use as solid waste disposal landfill site based on the criteria and available land area.

The study concluded by selecting five sites out of the final ten optimal sites as possible candidate sites for a solid waste landfill site in the study area. This was based on

the suitability index of the alternative sites which was computed using weights from the pairwise comparison of criteria.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are being made after this research;

1. Before the construction of a landfill facility on the suitable and selected sites; geological studies, special purpose engineering and hydro-geological studies should be conducted prior to siting as it wasn't done in this research work since this was beyond the scope of this study.
2. GIS and MCDA approach should be incorporated into the selection process for siting landfills so as to reduce the cost and time involved in the process as well as making the best decisions based on the criteria chosen.
3. The final decision on where a landfill should be sited is a political decision as much as it's a scientific one that is greatly influenced by public opinion. Hence, the public should be made to have a consensus on all of the most suitable candidate sites as it is critical to a successful running of operation and construction and shouldn't be overlooked. The "Not in My Backyard" (NIMBY) syndrome is usually a concern by many people especially for facilities that aren't aesthetically pleasing and causes economic drawdown on the properties of landed properties. So all relevant stakeholders in the community and selection process is needed to avoid cause for opposition in the future.

REFERENCE

- Abbas, S.M., Belhocine, N., ElGanainy, A.A. and Horton, M., 2010. A historical public debt database.
- Abou-Hadid, A.F., Medany, M.A., Abdrabbo, M., Hassanein, M.K., Farag, A.A., Abolmaaty, S.M., Khalil, A.A., Refaie, K.M., Saleh, S.M., Hashem, F.A. and Ismael, A.A., 2010. Preliminary studies using GIS and field survey to determine land cover in Egypt. *Arab Universities Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 18(1), pp.229-236.
- Ajibade, F.O., Olajire, O.O., Ajibade, T.F., Nwogwu, N.A., Lasisi, K.H., Alo, A.B., Owolabi, T.A. and Adewumi, J.R., 2019. Combining multicriteria decision analysis with GIS for suitably siting landfills in a Nigerian state. *Environmental and Sustainability Indicators*, 3, p.100010.
- Alanbari, M.A., Al-Ansari, N. and Jasim, H.K., 2014. GIS and multicriteria decision analysis for landfill site selection in AL-HashimiyahQadaa. *Natural Science*, 6(5), pp.282-304.
- Alkaradaghi, K., Ali, S.S., Al-Ansari, N., Laue, J. and Chabuk, A., 2019. Landfill site selection using MCDM methods and GIS in the Sulaimaniyah Governorate, Iraq. *Sustainability*, 11(17), p.4530.
- Allen, T., Christopher, B., Elias, V. and DeMaggio, J., 2001. *Development of the simplified method for internal stability design of mechanically stabilized earth walls* (No. WA-RD 513.1.). The Department.
- Amasuomo, E. and Baird, J., 2016. The concept of waste and waste Management. *J. Mgmt. & Sustainability*, 6, p.88.
- Amini, H.R., Reinhart, D.R. and Mackie, K.R., 2012. Determination of first-order landfill gas modeling parameters and uncertainties. *Waste management*, 32(2), pp.305-316.

- Blaurock-Busch, E., Friedle, A., Godfrey, M., Schulte-Uebbing, C.E. and Smit, C., 2010. Metal exposure in the children of Punjab, India. *Clinical Medicine Insights: Therapeutics*, 2, pp.CMT-S5154.
- Borouhaki, S. and Malczewski, J., 2010. ParticipatoryGIS: a web-based collaborative GIS and multicriteria decision analysis. *Urisa Journal*, 22(1), p.23.
- Cantwell, I., 1999. Society and Settlement in Glendalough and the Vartry before 1650. *Unpublished Undergraduate Dissertation, Geography Department, Trinity College Dublin*.
- Chalvatzaki, E. and Lazaridis, M., 2010. Estimation of greenhouse gas emissions from landfills: application to the Akrotiri landfill site (Chania, Greece). *Global NEST Journal*, 12(1), pp.108-116.
- Chalvatzaki, E. and Lazaridis, M., 2010. Estimation of greenhouse gas emissions from landfills: application to the Akrotiri landfill site (Chania, Greece). *Global NEST Journal*, 12(1), pp.108-116.
- Chang, N.B., Parvathinathan, G. and Breeden, J.B., 2008. Combining GIS with fuzzy multicriteria decision-making for landfill siting in a fast-growing urban region. *Journal of environmental management*, 87(1), pp.139-153.
- Chen, H., Lin, G.W., Lu, M.H., Shih, T.Y., Horng, M.J., Wu, S.J. and Chuang, B., 2011. Effects of topography, lithology, rainfall and earthquake on landslide and sediment discharge in mountain catchments of southeastern Taiwan. *Geomorphology*, 133(3-4), pp.132-142.
- Chen, N., Li, H. and Wang, L., 2009. A GIS-based approach for mapping direct use value of ecosystem services at a county scale: Management implications. *Ecological economics*, 68(11), pp.2768-2776.

- Clark, N.E., 2019. Blurred lines: Multi-use dynamics for satellite remote sensing. *Journal of International Humanitarian Legal Studies*, 10(1), pp.171-183.
- Danbuzu, L.A.S., Tanko, A.I., Ibrahim, U.A. and Ahmed, M., 2014. Spatial distribution of solid waste collection points using GIS approach in Urban Katsina, Katsina State, Nigeria. *American Journal of Engineering Research (AJER)*, 3(7), pp.107-116.
- Din, M.A.M., Jaafar, W.Z.W., Obot, M.M. and Hussin, W.M.A.W., 2008, May. How GIS can be a useful tool to deal with landfill site selection. In *International symposium on geoinformatics for spatial infrastructure development in earth and applied sciences* (Vol. 57).
- Drobne, S. and Lisec, A., 2009. Multi-attribute decision analysis in GIS: weighted linear combination and ordered weighted averaging. *Informatica*, 33(4).
Edition, p. 755-888.
- Esa, E. and Assen, M., 2017. A GIS based land suitability analysis for sustainable agricultural planning in Gelda catchment, Northwest Highlands of Ethiopia. *Journal of Geography and Regional Planning*, 10(5), pp.77-91.
- Esa, E. and Assen, M., 2017. A GIS based land suitability analysis for sustainable agricultural planning in Gelda catchment, Northwest Highlands of Ethiopia. *Journal of Geography and Regional Planning*, 10(5), pp.77-91.
- Farr, T.G., Rosen, P.A., Caro, E., Crippen, R., Duren, R., Hensley, S., Kobrick, M., Paller, M., Rodriguez, E., Roth, L. and Seal, D., 2007. The shuttle radar topography mission. *Reviews of geophysics*, 45(2).
- Feizizadeh, B. and Ghorbanzadeh, O., 2017. GIS-based interval pairwise comparison matrices as a novel approach for optimizing an analytical hierarchy process and multiple criteria weighting. *GI_Forum*, 1, pp.27-35.

- Getahun, K., 2020. *Gis Based Multi-Criteria Analysis For Suitable Solid Waste Disposal Site Selection: A Case of Tarcha Town* (Doctoral dissertation, ASTU).
- Ghana Landfill Guidelines, (2002). Best Practice Environmental Guidelines, 1.Environmental Protection Agency, Ghana.
- Ghoutum, A., Edith, K.W. and Lebga, A.K., Landfill Site Suitability Selection Using Geospatial Technology for the Yaounde Metropolitan City and its Environs: Case of Soa Subdivision, Cameroon.
- González-Gallina, A., Hidalgo-Mihart, M.G., Pérez-Garduza, F., Iglesias-Hernández, J.A., de Ita, A.O., Chacón-Hernández, A. and Vázquez-Zúñiga, O., 2018. Home range of a male jaguar spatially associated with the landfill of the city of Playa del Carmen, Mexico. *Mammalia*, 82(1), pp.54-61.
- Griffin, G.P. and Sener, I.N., 2016. Planning for bike share connectivity to rail transit. *Journal of public transportation*, 19(2), p.1.
- Halder, J.C., 2013. Land suitability assessment for crop cultivation by using remote sensing and GIS. *Journal of geography and Geology*, 5(3), p.65.
- Harries, K. and LeBeau, J., 2007. Issues in the geographic profiling of crime: review and commentary. *Police Practice & Research*, 8(4), pp.321-333.
- Hu, L., Liu, Y., Zeng, G., Chen, G., Wan, J., Zeng, Y., Wang, L., Wu, H., Xu, P., Zhang, C. and Cheng, M., 2017. Organic matters removal from landfill leachate by immobilized Phanerochaete chrysosporium loaded with graphitic carbon nitride under visible light irradiation. *Chemosphere*, 184, pp.1071-1079.
- Hutton, G., Haller, L., Water, S. and World Health Organization, 2004. *Evaluation of the costs and benefits of water and sanitation improvements at the global level* (No. WHO/SDE/WSH/04.04). World Health Organization.

- Ikhile, C.I., 2016. Geomorphology and hydrology of the Benin region, Edo state, Nigeria. *International Journal of Geosciences*, 7(02), p.144.
- Information Systems. *Environmental Geology*, 49. p. 376–388. doi: 10.1007/s00254-005-
- Israel, B.A., Lichtenstein, R., Lantz, P., McGranaghan, R., Allen, A., Guzman, J.R., Softley, D. and Maciak, B., 2001. The Detroit community-academic urban research center: development, implementation, and evaluation. *Journal of public health management and practice: JPHMP*, 7(5), pp.1-19.
- Jain, K. and Subbaiah, Y.V., 2007. Site suitability analysis for urban development using GIS. *Journal of Applied Sciences*, 7(18), pp.2576-2583.
- Jankowski, P. and Nyerges, T., 2001. GIS-supported collaborative decision making: Results of an experiment. *Annals of the Association of American Geographers*, 91(1), pp.48-70.
- Jankowski, P., 1995. Integrating geographical information systems and multiple criteria decision-making methods. *International journal of geographical information systems*, 9(3), pp.251-273.
- Joseph, K., 2002. Perspectives of solid waste management in India. In *international symposium on the technology and management of the treatment and reuse of the municipal solid waste, Shanghai, China* (pp. 15-20).
- Kaoje, I.U., Dankani, I.M. and Ishiaku, I., 2016. Site suitability analysis for municipal solid waste disposal in Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 21(7), pp.01-10.
- Karthikeyan, O.P. and Joseph, K., 2006. Bioreactor landfills for sustainable solid waste management. *Kavazanjian Jr, E., Matasovic, N., & Stokoe, KH (1996). II, and Bray, JD (1996). Insitu shear wave velocity of solid waste from surface wave measurements. Environmental Geotechnics, Edited by M. Kamon, AA Balkema, Rotterdam, the Netherlands, 1, pp.97-102.*

- Kayhanian, M. and Tchobanoglous, G., 1993. Innovative two-stage process for the recovery of energy and compost from the organic fraction of municipal solid waste (MSW). *Water Science and Technology*, 27(2), pp.133-143.
- Keith, J.M., Adams, P., Stephen, S. and Mattick, J.S., 2008. Delineating slowly and rapidly evolving fractions of the *Drosophila* genome. *Journal of Computational Biology*, 15(4), pp.407-430.
- Kokaly, R.F., Clark, R.N., Swayze, G.A., Livo, K.E., Hoefen, T.M., Pearson, N.C., Wise, R.A., Benzel, W.M., Lowers, H.A., Driscoll, R.L. and Klein, A.J., 2017. Usgs spectral library version 7 data: Us geological survey data release. *United States Geological Survey (USGS): Reston, VA, USA*.
- Kontos, T.D., Komilis, D.P. and Halvadakis, C.P., 2005. Siting MSW landfills with a spatial multiple criteria analysis methodology. *Waste management*, 25(8), pp.818-832.
- Li, D. and Lu, M., 2018. Integrating geometric models, site images and GIS based on Google Earth and Keyhole Markup Language. *Automation in Construction*, 89, pp.317-331.
- Lin, H.Y. and Kao, J.J., 1999. Enhanced spatial model for landfill siting analysis. *Journal of environmental engineering*, 125(9), pp.845-851.
- Magesh, N.S., Chandrasekar, N. and Soundranayagam, J.P., 2012. Delineation of groundwater potential zones in Theni district, Tamil Nadu, using remote sensing, GIS and MIF techniques. *Geoscience frontiers*, 3(2), pp.189-196.
- Malczewski, J., (1997). Propagation of errors in multi criteria location analysis: A case study. *Multi Criteria Decision Making: Proceedings of the 12th International Conference*, Hagan, Germany, p. 154-155. Retrieved January 15, 2015, from New York: Springer online database

- Malczewski, J., (2004). GIS-based land-use suitability analysis: A Critical Overview. *Progress in Planning*, 62, p.3-65.
- Malczewski, J., (2006). GIS-based multicriteria decision analysis: A survey of the literature. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 20:7, p. 703–726.
- Martín-de Castro, G., Delgado-Verde, M., Amores-Salvadó, J. and Navas-López, J.E., 2013. Linking human, technological, and relational assets to technological innovation: exploring a new approach. *Knowledge Management Research & Practice*, 11(2), pp.123-132.
- Miezah, K., Obiri-Danso, K., Kádár, Z., Fei-Baffoe, B. and Mensah, M.Y., 2015. Municipal solid waste characterization and quantification as a measure towards effective waste management in Ghana. *Waste management*, 46, pp.15-27.
- Nwambuonwo, O.J. and Mughele, E.S., 2012. Using geographic information system to select suitable landfill sites for megacities (case study of Lagos, Nigeria). *Computing, Information Systems & Development Informatics*, 3(4), pp.48-56.
- Nwankwoala, H.O., Eludoyin, O.S. and Obafemi, A.A., 2012. Groundwater quality assessment and monitoring using geographic information systems (GIS) in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *Ethiopian Journal of Environmental Studies and Management*, 5(4), pp.583-596.
- Oh, E., Lee, E., Im, H., Kang, H.S., Jung, W.W., Won, N.H., Kim, E.M. and Sul, D., 2005. Evaluation of immuno-and reproductive toxicities and association between immunotoxicological and genotoxicological parameters in waste incineration workers. *Toxicology*, 210(1), pp.65-80.
- Oyinloye, M.A., 2013. Using GIS and remote sensing in urban waste disposal and management: A focus on Owo LGA, Ondo State, Nigeria. *European International Journal of Science and Technology*, 2(7), pp.106-118.

- Raza, S.M.H., Mahmood, S.A., Khan, A.A. and Liesenberg, V., 2018. Delineation of potential sites for rice cultivation through multi-criteria evaluation (MCE) using remote sensing and GIS. *International Journal of Plant Production*, 12(1), pp.1-11.
- Satari, B. and Karimi, K., 2018. Citrus processing wastes: Environmental impacts, recent advances, and future perspectives in total valorization. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 129, pp.153-167.
- Sener, B., Suzen, L., & Doyuran, V., (2006). Landfill site selection by using Geographic Information Systems. *Environmental Geology*, 49(3), pp.376-388.
- Şener, B., Süzen, M.L. and Doyuran, V., 2006. Landfill site selection by using geographic information systems. *Environmental geology*, 49(3), pp.376-388.
- Şener, B., Süzen, M.L. and Doyuran, V., 2006. Landfill site selection by using geographic information systems. *Environmental geology*, 49(3), pp.376-388.
- Shelgikar, A.V., Anderson, P.F. and Stephens, M.R., 2016. Sleep tracking, wearable technology, and opportunities for research and clinical care. *Chest*, 150(3), pp.732-743.
- Tchobanoglous, G. & Frank K., (2002). Handbook of Solid Waste Management, Second Edition, McGraw-Hill, New York.
- Tchobanoglous, G., (2003). Solid Waste Management. Environmental Engineering, Fifth Edition, McGraw-Hill, New York.
- Tchobanoglous, G., Hilary, T., & Samuel, V., (1993). Integrated Solid Waste Management Engineering Principles and Management issues, p.7, McGraw-Hill, New York.
- Thompson, D.W., Solomon, S., Kushner, P.J., England, M.H., Grise, K.M. and Karoly, D.J., 2011. Signatures of the Antarctic ozone hole in Southern Hemisphere surface climate change. *Nature geoscience*, 4(11), pp.741-749.
- Wang, W., Qiao, X., Yang, S. and Wang, D., 2017. Present-day velocity field and block kinematics of Tibetan Plateau from GPS measurements. *Geophysical Journal International*, 208(2), pp.1088-1102.

- Wang, Y.Q., Zhang, X.Y. and Draxler, R.R., 2009. TrajStat: GIS-based software that uses various trajectory statistical analysis methods to identify potential sources from long-term air pollution measurement data. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 24(8), pp.938-939.
- Wang, Y.Q., Zhang, X.Y. and Draxler, R.R., 2009. TrajStat: GIS-based software that uses various trajectory statistical analysis methods to identify potential sources from long-term air pollution measurement data. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 24(8), pp.938-939.
- World Bank (2004). Sanitary Landfill Siting and Design Guidance. Guidance Published in May 1996 by the World Bank as an Urban Infrastructure Note, updated in November 2004.
- Yandle, T. and Burton, D., 1996. Reexamining environmental justice: A statistical analysis of historical hazardous waste landfill siting patterns in metropolitan Texas. *Social science quarterly*, pp.477-492.
- Yesilnacar, M.I., Süzen, M.L., Kaya, B.Ş. and Doyuran, V., 2012. Municipal solid waste landfill site selection for the city of Şanlıurfa-Turkey: an example using MCDA integrated with GIS. *International Journal of Digital Earth*, 5(2), pp.147-164.
- Yesilnacar, M.I., Süzen, M.L., Kaya, B.Ş. and Doyuran, V., 2012. Municipal solid waste landfill site selection for the city of Şanlıurfa-Turkey: an example using MCDA integrated with GIS. *International Journal of Digital Earth*, 5(2), pp.147-164.
- Zotos, G., A. Karagiannidis, S. Zampetoglou, Apostolos Malamakis, I-S. Antonopoulos, Stamatia Kontogianni, and George Tchobanoglous. "Developing a holistic strategy for integrated waste management within municipal planning: Challenges, policies, solutions and perspectives for Hellenic municipalities in the zero-waste, low-cost direction." *Waste Management* 29, no. 5 (2009): 1686-1692.